

Renewal of Economic Thinking in Vietnam in the Period 1986 - 1991: From Theoretical Perception to Practical Policy Making

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Abstract

In the context of complex world developments and the socio-economic crisis in the country, Vietnam faced many difficulties, especially in the economy. Therefore, in the period of 1986 - 1991, the Communist Party of Vietnam abolished the centralized, bureaucratic, subsidized economic mechanism, developed according to the market mechanism under state management, and built a multi-sector commodity economy, in which the state economy played a leading role. Due to the breakthrough innovation in economic thinking, the production and business activities of factories and enterprises were put into operation with high productivity and efficiency, meeting the consumption needs of the people, making the distribution and circulation of goods convenient. People's lives were significantly improved.

Keywords: *Innovation, 6th Party Congress, economic innovation, innovation in thinking.*

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Introduction

Amidst the turbulent global political situation, particularly the Soviet Union and other socialist countries facing a profound and comprehensive crisis in all aspects of social life, stemming from shortcomings and mistakes in policy and subjective idealism, the economy and politics were severely affected. In Vietnam, the economy was in a deadlock, inflation was high, production was stagnant, commodity prices were rising, and wages were insufficient to cover daily living expenses, causing significant hardship for cadres, party members, and the people. This was due to the Vietnamese Communist Party "maintaining for too long a centralized, bureaucratic, and subsidized mechanism when it was no longer suitable for a period when the country had entered the stage of peaceful reconstruction" (Song Thanh et al. 2008: 193). At the Sixth National Party Congress (1986), the Party deeply recognized practical experiences

and decided to innovate economic thinking, shifting from a centrally planned economy to a socialist-oriented market economy with state management. Therefore, the period 1986-1991 marked a transition from the old economic mechanism to a new one. This was a major shift in the Party's economic thinking, which subsequently boosted Vietnam's economic development and integration into the international economy.

Research Content and Results

Some Basic Concepts

The Concept of Innovation

The concept of innovation is mentioned in several Vietnamese dictionaries, such as: the comprehensive Vietnamese dictionary states that "Innovation is changing or making changes for the better, more progressive than before" (Nguyen Nhu Y et al. 1998: 348).

According to the Vietnamese dictionary: "Innovation is changing to be completely different from before, more progressive, overcoming backwardness and stagnation and meeting the requirements of development" (Hoang Phe et al. 2003: 337).

Innovation is mentioned by some authors in connection with the concept of change: P. Dejager states that "Change is the movement from an old state to a new state, the elimination of the old in the past and the acceptance of the new for the future" (2006: 286).

From the above perspectives, we can define innovation as a level of change, a change in the nature of things and phenomena towards a better, more progressive direction than before, meeting the requirements of development.

The concept of thinking

According to the Vietnamese dictionary: "Thinking is the highest stage of the cognitive process, delving into the essence and discovering the laws of things through forms such as symbols, concepts, judgments, and reasoning" (Hoang Phe et al. 2003: 1070).

Thinking is a form of organic matter, possessing a socio-historical nature, reflecting the natural world more deeply, faithfully, and completely, going infinitely deep, and approaching objective truth more closely. According to V.I. Lenin, "Human thinking—goes infinitely deep, from fantasy to essence, from first-level essence, if possible, to second-level essence... to infinity" (1977).

Nguyen Dinh Trai argued: "Thinking is the process of analyzing, synthesizing, and generalizing the materials obtained through sensory perception and empirical perception to deduce the general, the essence of things" (2001: 19).

We can offer the concept: Thinking is the process of perceiving things from sensory to rational through the analysis, synthesis, and generalization of the materials obtained, forming the general essence of things.

Economic Concept

In his work *Contribution to the Critique of Political Economy*, C. Marx affirmed: "In the social production of their lives, people have certain necessary relations, independent of their will – namely, relations of production, which correspond to a certain level of development of their material productive forces. The entirety of these relations of production constitutes the economic structure of society" (C. Marx and F. Engels 1993: 14-15).

In his letter to Bologna dated January 25, 1894, F. Engels wrote: "We understand economic relations – which we consider the decisive basis of social history – as the means by which people of a given society produce the means of subsistence and exchange products with one another" (C. Marx and F. Engels 1999: 270).

From the above concepts, we can summarize: economics is the ways and methods that people in a given society use to produce and exchange with each other. Thus, speaking of economics means speaking of the relationships between subjects within the totality of production relations that constitute the socio-economic structure, the infrastructure in a given society.

The concept of economic thinking innovation

Economic thinking innovation is a transformation in the way we perceive, interpret, and handle economic issues, thereby adjusting the system of viewpoints and policies to better suit reality and development requirements. Thinking innovation is not simply a replacement of content, but a change in thinking methods, a shift from subjective perception to a practical and scientific approach.

General Secretary Nguyen Phu Trong affirmed: "Renewing economic thinking is a change in the way of thinking about the goals, driving forces, methods and mechanisms of socio-economic development, in order to escape from stagnation and deadlock and move the country forward" (2006: 36). Renewing thinking is an important theoretical prerequisite for carrying out institutional and policy reforms.

Theoretical Understanding of Economic Reform

The Sixth National Congress of the Party affirmed: "...we are determined to make decisions that will turn the situation around, creating turning points for immediate development in order to achieve two basic goals: stabilizing the socio-economic situation; stabilizing and gradually improving the material and cultural life of the people" (Song Thanh et al. 2008: 194). The urgent issue raised during this period was the need to innovate economic thinking, that is, to stabilize the socio-economic situation, stabilize the people's lives, and help the people feel secure and confident in the Party's reform policies. The necessary task is to promote the sustainable development of the national economy, based on the old foundations. At the same time, the Party and the people need to understand their own internal strengths and inherit achievements from abroad, building a solid and long-lasting infrastructure foundation to become a country that is "peaceful, unified, independent, democratic, and prosperous" (Ho Chi Minh 2014: 3). From practical experiences in Ho Chi Minh City, Nguyen Van Linh had the experience of "seeking a path to doing business" in accordance with the laws of economic development to promote economic development, contributing to resolving the crisis, stabilizing production and people's lives, and maintaining political stability. This is the experience of reforming economic management in eliminating the centralized, bureaucratic, and subsidized mechanism to ensure the autonomy of production and business. At the Second Central Committee Conference, the General Secretary analyzed: "Distribution and circulation include many constituent parts such as prices, circulation of materials and goods, finance – budget, banking, wages... Distribution and circulation are both conditions and results of production. Thus, solving the problem of distribution and circulation is closely related to the production process, to the overall mechanism of national economic management" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 50). This is a key issue to break down the bottlenecks that previously existed in the economy, creating a driving force for economic development. After

the Conference, the Resolution spread widely into the lives of the people, especially greatly affecting the production and circulation of goods, gradually overcoming the obstacles to "inputs" and "outputs" of the production process, and paying attention to and addressing the economic interests of working people in a timely and appropriate manner. Furthermore, the General Secretary directed that the exchange and trade of goods should be expanded, "linking and self-regulating food supply between areas with surplus and areas with shortages" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 99), and all sectors "have the right to freely circulate and consume food" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 99), eliminating the situation of "prohibiting circulation and dividing the market according to administrative boundaries" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 76) in order to help stabilize the lives of the people. Policies on prices, wages, budget, and currency were also adequately addressed. Inflation tended to decrease, monetary circulation was stabilized, wages were balanced according to money and goods, gradually shifting from a distribution-based economy to a market-based economy with state guidance. As a result, the lives of the people were gradually stabilized and improved.

To keep pace with socio-economic development trends, reforming the economic management mechanism is essential and crucial. General Secretary Nguyen Van Linh pointed out that the agricultural sector is considered a crucial front, contributing to the successful implementation of the "three target programs on food, consumer goods, and export goods" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006a: 733). These programs, when reformed, must be implemented synchronously and closely linked with national defense and security to form a solid and sustainable bloc. One of the first tasks considered urgent for this breakthrough is addressing inflation. Currently, inflation is becoming a serious problem in our economy. It has spread throughout society, affecting even housewives, children, and all citizens. Because of the soaring prices of goods, buying candy and snacks for children has become a difficult issue. Although the state has invested an excessively large amount of money in circulation (10 times more), while the total

social product only increases by 6-7% per year, inflation could begin here. But the task we must now do is to confront this major challenge. General Secretary Nguyen Van Linh clearly stated: "...inflation is the combined manifestation of many factors, directly caused by large budget deficits, prices rising at an exorbitant rate, and a significant part due to arbitrary price increases to profit from price differences and competitive buying and selling. The deep and fundamental cause of the situation is low production, supply far from demand, and an imbalance between money and goods" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 51). Besides this cause, there may also be some people who have hoarded goods in large quantities to wait for an opportunity to sell them. It is also inevitable that some places will take advantage of the rising prices of goods to produce counterfeit, imitation, and substandard products, etc. The General Secretary affirmed: "...the direct cause of inflation is the continuous budget deficit and chaotic, soaring prices" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 52). Therefore, the immediate task is to promote the production and business activities of factories and enterprises to operate with high productivity and efficiency, meeting the consumption needs of the people and facilitating the distribution and circulation of goods.

Practical Aspects of Economic Reform Policy Planning

General Secretary Nguyen Van Linh outlined three tasks to be addressed in the first step: "Policies on prices and circulation of materials and goods. Policies and measures to limit budget deficits and reduce the rate of inflation. Policies and measures to address wages and living conditions of wage earners" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 52). Simultaneously, to successfully implement this step, four reductions must be immediately implemented: "Reducing budget deficits, gradually reducing the rate of price increases, reducing the rate of inflation, reducing difficulties in the lives of working people, contributing to liberating productive forces, expanding commodity exchange, and shifting economic activities to socialist business accounting" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 52). Initially, the economy implemented

market-based pricing mechanisms with a socialist orientation, starting "from consumer goods, agricultural products, raw materials, to means of production" (Song Thanh et al. 2008: 195). Agriculture is clearly the leading sector, but the economic structure needs to be restructured to align with the three key economic programs: "...foodstuffs, consumer goods, and export goods" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 53). Therefore, the most fundamental and urgent task today is to promote efficient distribution and circulation, liberate labor power and production productivity throughout society, and ensure the goals of the three economic programs are met. General Secretary Nguyen Van Linh directed: "Reforming pricing policies, in conjunction with reforming mechanisms, policies, and the organization of material and goods circulation, must actively contribute to stimulating production, expanding circulation, eliminating negative phenomena that cause prices to skyrocket, and promoting the implementation of socialist accounting and business practices" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 66). From now on, in addition to the mandatory tax payments by the people, other exchange relationships between farmers and state economic organizations "must follow the principles of equality, fair prices, mutual benefit, and buying and selling based on genuine agreement" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006b: 66). Thanks to this, farmers become masters of their land. They have the right to decide on cultivation according to market demands and the right to buy and sell their products to anyone at appropriate prices. This serves as encouragement and motivation for farmers to work diligently and actively in production, showcasing their individual farming abilities. They can also exchange and learn from each other's experiences, linking up in the production process to increase labor productivity and product quality, creating a competitive advantage when supplying products to the market. The state must ensure the supply of raw materials for agriculture, including essential goods for people's lives, at fair prices. These prices are regulated by the state according to different regions, but are consistent with the living standards of the people. In other words,

the state controls prices in the market, minimizing free markets that cause price fluctuations and negatively impact people's lives.

To stabilize market prices, the state restructured the economic sectors, with the state-owned economy playing a leading role, and other sectors playing an active and supporting role. However, those sectors that were no longer suitable were scaled down or eliminated to allow other sectors to operate and develop. This restructuring of the economic sectors enabled farmers to buy and sell agricultural products directly through a single point of contact, including the purchase of supplies and raw materials for agriculture and other goods. This reduced production costs, allowing farmers to make a profit from their agricultural investments. From there, our country's economy truly entered a period of "open market" in many localities across the country.

General Secretary Nguyen Van Linh had high expectations for the further development of our country's agriculture, as its potential for production is enormous, and it is necessary to quickly address the issue of unleashing productive forces in the labor force. In April 1988, the Politburo issued Resolution 10-NQ/TW on "Reforming Management in Agriculture," emphasizing that peasant households in agriculture are autonomous economic units in rural areas, receiving long-term land leases, having autonomy in cultivation and business on leased land, and encouraging all forms of investment in agriculture. Resolution 10 truly freed those engaged in production and business to be more proactive, flexible, and creative than Directive 100 (1981) on improving the contract system, expanding "product-based contracts to labor groups and individual workers" in agricultural cooperatives. It truly unleashed a powerful force of rural productivity. The Party identified the household as an individual economic component, promoting economic development. By the end of 1988, the whole country implemented a monetary system replacing wages, abolishing the subsidy system, and distributing goods according to quotas using ration coupons. Our State decided to gradually shift from a barter economy to a market-based economy with state management.

The policy of the Communist Party of Vietnam did not stop at resolutions and policies but needed to be institutionalized into law to quickly implement it in practice. General Secretary Nguyen Van Linh also paid attention to the issue of whether businesses were profitable or not among different economic sectors in order to quickly develop appropriate mechanisms. The General Secretary's attention became a strong catalyst, spreading throughout the entire political system. In November 1987, the Council of Ministers (now the Government) of our country issued Decision No. 217/HĐBT on "Reforming socialist planning and accounting for state-owned enterprises." This timely and wise decision helped state-owned enterprises become autonomous in production and business, independently carrying out accounting, using revenue to offset expenses in order to generate profits. Just one month later, the President issued the Law on Foreign Investment to attract investment from countries in the region and around the world (regardless of nationality) into Vietnam's economy, offering many advantages and preferential provisions. In 1987, the Council of Ministers created a favorable legal framework for domestic enterprises to invest and develop. The government developed a new tax policy and expanded banking operations, such as establishing specialized banks, commercial banks, and operating under an accounting mechanism. The gold, silver, gemstone, and jewelry trading industry was liberalized, allowing all economic sectors to engage in business (no longer dependent on state subsidies as in the previous centrally planned economy). Notably, this was the first time the global currency market was opened, with exchange rates being determined according to international rates, increasing the accuracy and reliability of the global currency market. With specific shifts in the financial and monetary price mechanisms of the world, in 1989 our country truly had a unified price market with a single price mechanism. General Secretary Nguyen Van Linh emphasized: "Transform all economic units, especially state-owned enterprises, to a business mechanism linked to the market, operating on the principles of self-sufficiency, self-development, and fulfilling the obligation to

contribute to the state budget” (Communist Party of Vietnam 2006c: 977).

Following the spirit of President Ho Chi Minh's Testament, General Secretary Nguyen Van Linh provided close guidance on the country's socio-economic situation, paying attention to the lives of the people, especially farmers and hardworking laborers who needed appropriate policies. In 1989, the state issued a decision to exempt agricultural taxes by 50% for two years (1989-1990) for agricultural cooperatives, production groups, and farmers. Regarding the industrial and service sectors, the Council of Ministers issued Decrees No. 27, 28, and 29, specifying the individual and collective economic sectors to promote the strong growth and development of industrial production, services, construction, and transportation. These decrees contributed to the formation of a solid legal framework that encouraged investment and development of these economic sectors, significantly increasing compared to before.

Results and Significance of Economic Reforms

From the very beginning of the Doi Moi (Renovation) period, the Communist Party of Vietnam determined to abolish the centralized bureaucratic and subsidized system, eliminating the "blocking of rivers and markets" in production and circulation. The Party chose agriculture as the most crucial and priority sector. Based on this, it used distribution and circulation as the driving force to achieve the goals of three key economic programs: food, consumer goods, and exports. The domestic food situation has improved significantly, from a state of severe shortage to a recovery, meeting the needs of the people, creating reserves, and enabling exports. In March 1987, the Central Committee meeting assessed agricultural production nationwide and concluded that agricultural production had become one of the great economic achievements, contributing to social development. The Vietnamese economy gradually recovered and developed. “The inflation rate decreased, reaching only 67.4% in 1990 (compared to 774.7% in 1986). In 1987, agricultural production reached 17.5 million tons of food, in 1988 it reached 19.5 million tons, and

in 1989 it reached 20.5 million tons” (Doan The Hanh 2010). From 1989, Vietnam began exporting rice to the world in large quantities, “1.4 million tons of rice - ranking third in the world after Thailand and the United States...” (Nguyen Dai Lai 2008). “Export turnover in 1986 was 439 million rubles and 384 million USD. In 1990, it increased to 1,019 million rubles and 1,179 million USD. The average annual economic growth rate from 1986 to 1990 was 3.9%” (Doan The Hanh 2010). This was the first step in building prestige and success among countries in the region and around the world. “This is a strategically significant victory; it marks the beginning of stability and an increase in the country's food supply, making an important contribution to the country's political stability” (Song Thanh et al. 2008: 196).

Renewing economic thinking is crucial in stabilizing people's lives and improving the balance of exports and imports. We should not be complacent or dogmatic, as this would hinder economic development and negatively impact people's lives. The Party and the State must have reasonable policies and guidelines for economic development, especially when transitioning from a self-sufficient, centrally-managed, bureaucratic, and subsidized economy to a multi-sector commodity economy operating under a market mechanism with state management. This further demonstrates that the development of a multi-sector commodity economy must go hand in hand with strengthening the state's role in socio-economic management. This is absolutely necessary to unleash and develop the productive potential of society, such as better mobilization of social resources, control of inflation, and improvement of the people's material and spiritual lives. However, we should not underestimate the production of consumer goods while placing too much emphasis on heavy industrial production. We must not be complacent when the market economy develops because many negative consequences can occur. We soon had strategies and policies to "keep the reform process on the right track and promote the good nature of socialism" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2007: 89).

Today, the world is undergoing many rapid changes with new challenges such as climate change, technological competition, and geopolitical conflicts. Vietnam continues to uphold the spirit of innovative thinking to adapt and develop. Continuing to prioritize the interests of the people, considering the private sector as key, the state has been perfecting a rational legal and policy system, encouraging people to start businesses, innovate, and promote the role of the people and businesses as masters, thereby creating new momentum for the economy, ensuring a fair, transparent, efficient, and appropriate business environment in line with international requirements and standards. Thanks to the innovation in economic thinking, Vietnam proactively opens up opportunities in foreign relations in many aspects: multilateralization and diversification of relations; Joining international and regional organizations and participating in global value chains aims to enhance competitiveness and affirm Vietnam's position in the international arena. "Our country has never had such a foundation, potential, position, and international prestige as it does today" (Nguyen Phu Trong 2021: 25).

Conclusion

The renewal of economic thinking also marked a turning point in the formation of a multi-sector commodity economy operating under a market mechanism with state management. This was a long-term strategic policy during the transitional period to socialism, put forth by the Communist Party of Vietnam at its Sixth Central Committee Conference. This policy was supported by the people and quickly spread into their lives. It also helped the people exercise their right to self-governance in the economic field, "awakening many potentials and creative forces of the people to develop production and services, create more jobs and products for society; promoting the formation and development of a commodity economy, creating vibrant competition in the market" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2007: 59).

This issue requires the state to have an adaptive economic management mechanism, appropriate to each specific period in the economic reform

of Vietnam, including "price reform, circulation policies and expansion of foreign economic relations which have promoted the formation of a unified market nationwide linked to the world market" (Communist Party of Vietnam 2007: 60). The state increases investment and has reasonable policies to enable the entire population to participate and contribute through various economic sectors to the cause of national reform. Currently, the economic thinking reform in the period 1986-1991 is still illuminating Vietnam's development path in the new era, helping the country overcome challenges and reach new heights.

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